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Market mechanisms for scaling biomethane in industrial agriculture: Insights from a Delphi study

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ABSTRACT

Biomethane is emerging as a promising renewable energy source (RES) for reducing agricultural greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, improving nutrient management and strengthening energy security. When integrated into biorefinery systems, it can transform agricultural residues into renewable bioenergy and organic fertilisers, supporting circularity and sustainable development. However, uncertainties remain regarding how this transition technology will be governed and its real capacity to deliver lasting environmental benefits. Ireland's high-GHG-emitting agriculture and intensive dairy sector create a favourable context for biomethane development, yet progress remains uneven under existing energy policies. At the same time, a government-led biomethane strategy offers opportunities for systemic transition. This study examines the enabling conditions for circular bioeconomy (CBE) development in this context, focusing on how nutrient supply into anaerobic digesters and demand for renewable energy and bio-based fertilisers can be supported through well-functioning marketplaces. Using a modified Delphi method and structured risk classification, expert stakeholders from Ireland's dairy sector assessed future development pathways. The study highlights significant obstacles, including poor utilisation of digestate, lack of supply chain coordination, regulatory inconsistencies and financing difficulties. Biomethane is often seen only as a bioenergy source, but in order to truly contribute to sustainable development, it must be recognised as a multifunctional lever, capable of connecting agriculture, energy, society and the environment.

1. Introduction

The global dairy sector is a vital economic driver but also a significant contributor to environmental degradation. Livestock farming accounts for approximately 14.5 % of total anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions globally [1], with methane (CH₄) from enteric fermentation and nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane from livestock waste being major sources in dairy production [2]. Additionally, land use change—primarily the conversion of natural habitats to agricultural land—is the leading driver of biodiversity loss [3]. Extensive livestock systems drive deforestation and land degradation, while intensive systems contribute to nutrient overloads and pollution due to waste mismanagement [1]. Rising demand for animal products due to an ever-growing global population is only amplifying these pressures [4]. Therefore, agriculture must reconcile intensive approaches to food

production with biodiversity and ecosystem services provision—one of the most pressing challenges of the 21st century [5].

Within the European Union (EU), these pressures are highlighted by conflicting and interacting policy agendas. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), while increasingly integrating environmental conditionalities, has historically prioritised productivity, competitiveness and income support—contributing to agricultural intensification in many regions [6]. One of the most significant reforms to affect dairy production was the abolition of EU milk quotas in 2015, which enabled a major expansion of Ireland's dairy sector. This led to substantial growth in herd size and milk yields among both existing and new dairy farms, contributing to rising agricultural GHG emissions [7]. While this expansion bolstered economic growth, it also placed substantial pressure on land use, water quality and biodiversity, highlighting the environmental trade-offs inherent in intensification [8]. Simultaneously,

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environmental directives such as the Nitrates Directive (ND) and the Water Framework Directive (WFD) aim to mitigate pollution and protect aquatic ecosystems, placing constraints on nutrient management and land use. Financial and reporting regulations—including the EU Sustainable Finance Taxonomy (EUSFT), the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)—further reshape operational and strategic choices for agribusinesses, their suppliers (farmers) and their customers (food companies and retailers), who must navigate competing demands across productivity, sustainability and regulatory compliance.

Agribusinesses have adopted a range of strategies that appear to reconcile economic and environmental goals, but in practice often outmanoeuvre environmental priorities in response to growing regulatory and market pressures. Companies like *Kerry Group* and *Glanbia* have divested high-impact assets to cooperative structures, reducing exposure to stringent reporting requirements under the CSRD [9,10]. Similarly, herd reduction has been proposed as a short-term strategy to lower emissions by reducing animal numbers while increasing productivity over the longer term [11]. While these approaches can provide short-term relief, they fail to address systemic inefficiencies or capitalise on opportunities for long-term sustainability.

The increasing size and spatial concentration of dairy farms have amplified the environmental impacts of intensive livestock farming, particularly in regions with nutrient surpluses [12]. Improper manure handling contributes to regulatory scrutiny and heightened costs, necessitating effective mitigation strategies such as detailed manure management plans or improved nutrient recycling practices [13]. Beyond traditional approaches, manure can also serve as a renewable energy feedstock, presenting an opportunity to address environmental challenges while creating economic value. Through the conversion of manure into biomethane, i.e., a renewable energy source (RES) and nutrient-rich digestate, anaerobic digestion (AD) and broader biorefining strategies provide a circular bioeconomy (CBE) approach that reduces GHG emissions and transforms agricultural waste into value-added resources that could replace the reliance on chemical fertilisers [13,14]. In this way, the biorefining process not only support climate change mitigation by reducing GHG emissions but also promote more sustainable waste management practices within intensive livestock systems [15].

Ireland offers an interesting case study for exploring biomethane market development. As Ireland's largest emitter of GHGs, agriculture plays a crucial role in the country's decarbonisation efforts [16]. The National Biomethane Strategy aims to produce 5.7 TWh of biomethane annually by 2030, underscoring the urgency of decarbonising hard-to-abate sectors such as agriculture, energy and transport [14]. This initiative presents significant opportunities for the dairy industry to enhance both its environmental and economic resilience. However, Ireland's biomethane sector remains severely underdeveloped relative to other EU countries [17].

This contrast between policy ambition, apparent resource potential and limited market development highlights a broader gap in understanding how biorefining can be effectively governed and coordinated to deliver CBE outcomes in practice. Despite growing technological maturity and policy attention, existing research has tended to focus on technical feasibility and energy substitution, while issues related to market coordination, governance arrangements and the valorisation of co-products such as digestate remain underexplored [14,17]. As a result, there is limited empirical insight into the enabling conditions required to align environmental objectives with viable market structures in intensive agricultural systems such as Ireland's dairy sector.

To address this gap, the present study examines the conditions necessary for biomethane market development in Ireland's dairy sector, drawing on Roth's market design framework [18,19] as the guiding theoretical framework. Market design theory identifies key principles for well-functioning markets, including thickness, congestion management, safety and the mitigation of repugnance, alongside the supporting

infrastructure, rules, customs and social support required for successful implementation.

Drawing on this framework, the current paper seeks to answer the following questions (RQs) relating to how we can facilitate the supply of nutrients into anaerobic digesters and generate the demand for outputs, such as renewable energy and bio-based products:

RQ1: What are the key challenges and opportunities for biomethane market development within Ireland's dairy sector?

RQ2: What are the enabling conditions for a circular bioeconomy (CBE) in Ireland that addresses excess nutrients from intensive dairy production?

To answer these RQs, the study draws on expert insights gathered through a three-round modified Delphi process. Tuni et al.'s [20] ex-ante risk classification framework is central to this process, allowing the study to assess the pre-implementation perceptions of the key risks associated with the transition from linear to circular business models (CBMs).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the theoretical framework, drawing on market design principles and risk categorisation approaches. Section 3 describes the research design and methodology, including the modified Delphi process. Section 4 presents the results, identifying key barriers and enabling conditions. Section 5 discusses these findings in light of systemic circularity challenges and policy implications. Finally, Section 6 concludes by summarising the study's contributions, limitations and directions for future research.

2. Theoretical background

This section outlines the theoretical basis for analysing biorefinery as a pathway toward circularity in industrial agriculture. It first explores how biorefineries contribute to circular economy goals through organic waste valorisation. It then turns to market design theory to examine the enabling conditions for scaling biomethane production in Ireland's dairy sector.

2.1. Circular economy, circular waste management and business innovation

The European Commission released its second Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) in 2020, reinforcing the shift away from the linear "take-make-use-dispose" model towards a regenerative circular system [21]. The EU's shift towards a circular economy (CE) aims to reduce resource pressures, drive sustainable economic growth and generate employment opportunities while supporting its 2050 climate neutrality goals and efforts to curb biodiversity loss. Businesses are key to this transition, as CBMs provide new approaches to value creation, delivery and capture by slowing, closing or reducing material cycles in production processes [22,23]. CBMs take various forms, with resource recovery models playing a central role in closing material loops and ensuring that waste streams are repurposed into valuable secondary resources [24]. A key example of this is industrial symbiosis, where waste or by-products from one process become feedstock for another [23].

The global food system generates over three billion tonnes of animal waste annually, far exceeding the total weight of human waste, food waste and even global plastic production [25]. Despite its scale, this waste is often mismanaged, leading to acute environmental impacts such as nutrient runoff and methane emissions [26]. Poor waste management presents significant risks to companies. Given the high cost of inputs like feed and fertilisers, maximising the use of all materials and by-products is crucial for improving resource efficiency and reducing GHG emissions across the food value chain.

In this context, biorefining offers a solution, converting organic waste into renewable energy in the form of biogas (which can be

upgraded to biomethane) and nutrient-rich digestate. This can help reduce on-farm GHG emissions and decrease reliance on GHG-intensive chemical fertilisers and fossil fuels [25]. By closing nutrient loops, biorefining aligns with CBE objectives, promoting a more sustainable approach to waste and resource management [27]. However, while biorefining delivers clear environmental benefits, its effectiveness depends on the implementation of adequate nutrient management strategies to prevent unintended ecological consequences [28]. Life-cycle assessments indicate that while biorefinery reduces GHG emissions from manure, improper nutrient recycling can still contribute to eutrophication [25].

A simplified visual representation of the biorefinery process, along with its key inputs and outputs, is provided in Fig. 1 below.

Despite these potential benefits, Ireland lags behind its European counterparts in biorefinery adoption, primarily due to regulatory barriers and insufficient government incentives [17]. Nevertheless, Ireland has abundant biomass resources, creating significant potential for renewable energy production from agricultural waste at a relatively low cost [17]. Recognising this, the recently published National Biomethane Strategy outlines a plan to scale biomethane production to 5.7 TWh annually by 2030 [14]. The development of biogas and biomethane markets across Europe varies considerably, influenced by national policies, agricultural structures and waste management approaches [30].

Successfully transitioning to a CE/CBE requires coordinated action from both policymakers and industry actors [31]. This underscores the need to explore how the dairy sector can facilitate CBM adoption, ensuring nutrient loops are effectively closed while mitigating negative impacts on freshwater ecosystems. The success of such business models will depend not only on consistent inputs and stable demand, but also on the institutional mechanisms that enable the exchange, allocation and use of resources derived from organic waste. While biorefinery is often viewed through a technical or environmental lens, it is fundamentally a socio-economic system. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the process relies on a series of interdependent transactions—ranging from feedstock procurement to digestate application and energy distribution—which must be efficiently coordinated through rules, incentives, information flows and shared infrastructure.

Framing biorefinery as a set of marketplaces, rather than just a technical process, shifts attention to the enabling conditions that determine whether circular resource flows can be scaled and sustained. This opens up new analytical ground for understanding how economic theory—and market design in particular—can inform strategies for circular business model implementation. The following section draws on Roth's [19,20] market design framework to explore what structural features, rules and policy supports are required to develop a functional biomethane market within Ireland's dairy sector.

2.2. Market design framework for biomethane adoption

Market design, as outlined by Roth [18,19], focuses on building or improving markets. This may involve repairing markets that suffer from coordination failures, missing price signals or externalities—or constructing entirely new markets to support novel forms of exchange [19]. Crucially, marketplaces depend not only on economic incentives but also on the infrastructure, institutional rules, behavioural norms and information flows that shape how participants interact [19]. As Roth [19] emphasises, marketplaces also require a degree of social support to function effectively.

This framing is particularly valuable when considering how to support CBMs such as biorefining within the dairy sector. This study is interested in whether a circular economy can be created to help decarbonise Irish agriculture and reduce its environmental impact—particularly from nutrient pollution—by transforming excess nutrients into valuable products. At its simplest, biorefining can be understood as a system in which waste inputs (e.g., livestock slurry, food waste, wastewater) are converted into useful outputs (e.g., biomethane, digestate) (see Fig. 1). From a market design perspective, this entails creating functioning marketplaces that align the supply of nutrients with the demand for renewable energy and chemical fertiliser substitutes. These flows require more than technical viability—they depend on institutional coordination, trust, appropriate rules and sustained policy support. By applying a market design lens, the study aims to clarify what enabling conditions are needed to support the emergence of such marketplaces and ensure that the transition to circularity is both effective and equitable.

Roth [18] identifies four essential characteristics of well-functioning markets:

1. **Thickness** - Markets require a sufficient number of participants to enable transactions [18]. This concept captures the economic, social and environmental drivers that are expected to motivate companies to adopt biomethane production and the necessary political interventions to address internal and external barriers that otherwise hinder the transition [32,33]. Thickness may be prevented by competing alternatives. In the context of expected output from biorefineries, existing fossil fuel-based alternatives are less expensive. As Zhu et al. [30] explain, “*The simple reason why biogas merits public subsidy is that without support, fossil alternatives would predominate, as they are substantially cheaper. However, the environmental benefits associated with AD both on carbon emissions and water pollution provide justification for public support.*” This reflects a classic market failure, where positive externalities—such as GHG emissions reductions and

Fig. 1. Biorefinery inputs and outputs from anaerobic digestion (Adapted from Environmental and Energy Study Institute (EESI) [29] and Collier FAIRR [25]).

improved nutrient management—are not fully reflected in market prices, leading to underinvestment.

2. **Low congestion** - In resource recovery and industrial symbiosis models, multiple moving parts—from feedstock supply and transportation to digestate distribution and biomethane grid access—must align to ensure smooth operations. Roth [18] emphasises that markets must not only attract participants (thickness) but also avoid congestion by ensuring that transactions can occur efficiently. Blanco et al. [34] and Wu et al. [35] highlight that low congestion is essential for biomethane adoption, ensuring that logistical and market coordination challenges—such as feedstock competition, supply chain bottlenecks and AD plant placement inefficiencies—are addressed to enable smooth operations and sustained participation. This is echoed by Skovsgaard and Jacobsen [36], who show that while larger AD plants can benefit from economies of scale in capital and operational costs, these gains are often offset by rising transport costs, particularly when co-substrates must be sourced from dispersed or distant areas. Their findings underline the importance of regulatory flexibility to allow biogas producers to incorporate a wider range of alternative feedstocks, reducing exposure to location-based constraints and supporting more resilient and efficient supply chains.
3. **Safety** - Roth [18] highlights that a well-functioning market must provide participants with a safe environment, minimising uncertainty and potential strategic behaviour that could reduce overall welfare. CBM innovation is inherently uncertain, posing economic consequences and adoption challenges [37]. Tuni et al. [20] emphasise that ensuring safety is crucial for CBM adoption and it requires addressing perceived risks across market, supply, finance, political/regulatory and technical domains. A structured ex-ante risk assessment can mitigate uncertainties, enabling policymakers and industry stakeholders to remove barriers and support a smoother transition proactively.
4. **Address Repugnance** - A fourth, and potentially overlooked, design principle is social acceptance [18,19]. While technical feasibility and financial viability often dominate policy discussions, societal support plays a decisive role in shaping the success of biomethane markets. Paolini et al. [38] highlight that public concerns over environmental and health impacts, including air quality and digestate use, often hinder the acceptance of AD plants. Beyond these environmental and logistical factors, Planing [22] emphasises that resistance to circular business models also stems from entrenched consumer habits and social norms, which can challenge adoption even when economic and ecological benefits are clear. Mancini and Raggi [39] further identify social acceptance as the most prominent non-technical barrier to biogas project development, particularly around infrastructure siting and digestate use. Similarly, Bourdin and Delcayre [40] show that project scale matters: larger facilities often face stronger opposition unless they are perceived to respect the character and expectations of local communities. While focused on wind energy, Warren et al. [41] discuss “not in my backyard” (NIMBY) as a commonly referenced concept in debates around renewable energy infrastructure. However, their findings suggest that local opposition cannot be explained solely by proximity, but is shaped by a wider set of factors, including landscape perceptions, lived experience and planning processes. Taken together, these insights underscore that societal opposition is not simply a matter of poor communication, but a structural barrier that must be proactively addressed through participatory governance, fair benefit-sharing and context-sensitive project design.

While economic, social and environmental drivers create incentives for adoption, structural and institutional barriers necessitate targeted interventions to facilitate market growth. Tuni et al. [20] provide a risk classification framework for assessing the transition to CBMs. This framework closely aligns with Roth’s [18,19] market design approach

while specifying the characteristics of market risks as well as the necessary enabling conditions within the financial, political/regulatory and technical domains. The emergence of CBMs requires policy coherence and intervention packages that provide economic, regulatory and informational support [33,42,43]. Policy mixes, consisting of push-and-pull economic instruments, regulatory measures, research and education initiatives and information instruments, are available to policymakers to develop a roadmap for future market development [33].

Roth’s [18,19] market design principles and Tuni et al.’s [20] framework provide the analytical lens through which expert input is interpreted in this study (Fig. 2). The current study aims to identify the enabling conditions necessary for the emergence of circular business models and functioning marketplaces that address the challenges of excess nutrients in agriculture. While biomethane production forms a central part of this discussion, the study’s broader interest lies in how biorefining systems—including the valorisation of digestate—can support nutrient recovery, waste reduction and environmental restoration. Regulatory frameworks must not only foster innovation and attract investment but also safeguard against greenwashing and ensure genuine environmental benefits [44]. Striking this balance is essential—not simply to expand biomethane production, but to support the development of circular models that integrate economic and environmental objectives, positioning Ireland’s bioeconomy as a potential international example of sustainable agri-food system transformation.

3. Research method and design

3.1. The Delphi approach

This study employs a modified Delphi method, a structured, iterative approach designed to gather expert insights and build consensus on complex, multidimensional issues [45]. Initially developed by the RAND Corporation in the 1950s, the Delphi method is particularly well suited to forward-looking problems where empirical data are limited and expert judgement is the main source of insight [45,46]. It has been widely adopted in fields where expert judgment serves as the main source of insight and is particularly valuable for identifying areas of consensus and contention among diverse, multi-stakeholder groups on complex issues lacking definitive answers [46].

The Delphi process structures communication through successive rounds of questionnaires with controlled feedback, enabling experts to iteratively refine their views and reach a consensus of opinion that is as reliable as possible among a group of experts [47]. It rests on four main principles: anonymity, iteration, controlled feedback and statistical aggregation [48,49]. Anonymity minimises peer pressure and groupthink, iteration enables participants to reconsider views based on group responses, and controlled feedback and aggregation promote convergence [49,50]. Commonly employed in policy-making and problem-solving contexts, it is particularly suited for situations where complete knowledge is unavailable, providing a robust approach to forming collective expert opinions [51,52]. Research suggests that two to three rounds are typically sufficient to achieve a reliable level of consensus, balancing thoroughness and efficiency while avoiding participant fatigue [48]. Through this iterative refinement, the Delphi method captures nuanced insights, making it especially valuable in contexts such as biomethane market design, where cross-sector expertise is crucial for navigating complex financial, political and operational dynamics.

3.2. Expert selection and panel composition

Selecting appropriate experts is a critical—and often under-examined—component of the Delphi method [49]. Unlike methods based on representative sampling, Delphi panels are built around the purposive selection of individuals with deep subject-matter knowledge. This study’s expert panel was designed to include diverse perspectives, vital to understanding the multidimensional challenges of

Fig. 2. A theoretical framework combining market design principles (Roth [18,19]) and ex-ante risk identification (Tuni et al. [20]) to assess the enabling conditions for circular bioeconomy development.

mainstreaming biomethane within Ireland's CBE. The panel included representatives from academia, dairy processing, financial services and industry stakeholders. Experts were selected based on their knowledge in areas directly relevant to biomethane policy or practice, ensuring that practical insights into financial, regulatory and operational dimensions of biomethane adoption informed discussions. Although farmers play a vital role in supplying feedstock and applying bio-fertilisers, they encounter significant barriers—particularly around cost and technical capacity—highlighting the need for agribusiness support to drive broader systemic change [53].

Table 1 summarises the stakeholder groups and selection criteria used for expert identification. The expert panel was composed of professionals with significant domain expertise, many with over 10 years of experience in their respective fields. Participants represented diverse roles, including national policy, academic research, financial services and senior innovation leads from dairy cooperatives and industry clusters.

Snowball identification was used for all stakeholder types, with outreach expanded after each round, following a “cascade methodology” approach [55], where initial participants helped identify further experts across domains. Frewer et al. [55] describe this approach in the context of agrifood policy, noting that the first round is often exploratory in nature and may involve a smaller group of expert stakeholders to let key themes and uncertainties surface. This makes the relatively lower number of Round 1 participants appropriate in this case. The panel was subsequently expanded to include broader expertise in renewable energy and organic waste management, thereby strengthening diversity and legitimacy across rounds and supporting the aim of capturing a wide range of expert perspectives.

Table 1
Expert panel identification (Adapted from de Jesus et al. [54]).

Type of stakeholder	Criteria for sourcing panel members
Dairy processing - general/ Dairy sector - processing Financial service	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Industry professionals with operational, sustainability and innovation experience. ■ Professionals with experience in agricultural and green finance.
Public policy development/ implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Government and agency representatives involved in circular bioeconomy, energy or agri-policy.
Academic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Researchers with knowledge on circular bioeconomy, environmental technology or policy expertise.
Other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Cluster leads, cooperative managers, innovation officers and technical advisors involved in the dairy sector and/or circular bioeconomy.

The panel initially comprised 19 participants in Round 1, increasing to 31 in Round 2 and concluding with 42 in the final workshop and breakout rooms (Fig. 3). While Delphi studies often experience participant attrition, panel expansion across rounds is acceptable when the goal is to measure a diversity of expert opinions rather than steer the group toward strict consensus. As noted by the British Psychological Society (BPS) [56], “if the Delphi process is a means of measuring opinions, fewer rounds are generally acceptable. Having a complete dataset is less vital, and the panel can be expanded across rounds by inviting more panellists in Round 2.” In this case, later rounds benefited from broader outreach and reputational engagement. Crucially, diversity and balance were maintained throughout to ensure representativeness [46].

This design choice aligns with the analytical approach: open-ended responses were thematically analysed using qualitative content analysis, while closed-ended responses were evaluated using simple descriptive statistics (i.e., frequency and proportion counts).

3.3. Modifications to the traditional Delphi approach

In its original form, the Delphi method focused on multiple rounds of anonymised surveys to arrive at a consensus. However, it has since been adapted in many fields to include elements such as in-person discussion and formal consensus thresholds [46,57,58]. This study adopts a modified Delphi approach, integrating two rounds of surveys followed by an online, real-time workshop. This format was designed to combine the structured anonymity of early rounds with the benefits of dynamic interaction in the final round. In highly interdisciplinary fields such as biorefinery and CBE, this hybrid approach is particularly valuable [55, 58].

While anonymity was preserved in the first two rounds, the final round invited participants to engage openly in a 3.5-hour moderated workshop via *Microsoft Teams*. This adaptation was essential to foster deeper participant interaction and facilitate comprehensive dialogue on more contentious issues. This is consistent with adaptations in other Delphi studies where face-to-face interaction was shown to resolve nuanced or contested issues more effectively than survey-only designs [59].

Moderators ensured that the workshop environment was safe, balanced and inclusive—particularly for participants from the Irish dairy sector, where prior research has identified scepticism toward climate policy and perceptions of unfair blame in public discourse [57, 60,61]. Breaking anonymity allowed for trust-building and helped frame dairy actors as active partners in shaping Ireland’s climate, water and biodiversity strategies. The integration of structured survey rounds and open discussion allowed the study to combine the independence of the Delphi process with the consensus-building dynamics of deliberative

Fig. 3. Respondents per survey rounds, total number and sectoral distribution (Adapted from de Jesus et al. [54]).

Note: A detailed breakdown of panel composition is provided in Appendix A (Fig. 7) for the workshop breakout groups, with full details for all survey rounds reported in Supplementary Table S1.

processes, ultimately helping to converge perspectives across a diverse stakeholder group.

3.4. Data analysis

This study employed a three-round modified Delphi process to engage expert stakeholders in identifying and interpreting the barriers and enabling conditions for CBE development in Ireland's dairy sector. The process is summarised in Fig. 4.

- **Round 1** gathered broad exploratory insights through a mixed-method survey (primarily open-ended, with some closed and ranking questions). Participants were asked to identify key barriers, research priorities and enabling factors relating to nutrient circularity, finance, infrastructure, innovation and policy. Responses were collected using the *Qualtrics* survey platform.
- **Round 2** used a structured survey format to refine and prioritise the risks identified in Round 1. Drawing on the framework developed by Tuni et al. [20] participants ranked the most critical barriers across five domains: supply, market, finance, policy/regulation, and technology. These responses were also collected using the *Qualtrics* survey platform.
- **Round 3** consisted of a 3.5-hour interactive online workshop hosted on *Microsoft Teams*, designed to validate and deepen the findings from Round 2. Breakout discussions were organised around the four core domains of supply, market, finance and policy/regulation, with participants co-developing targeted recommendations. Audio recordings and transcripts from the session were analysed qualitatively to capture key points of agreement, divergence and suggested actions.

A mixed-methods analytical approach was used throughout. Open-ended responses were analysed using qualitative content analysis to identify recurring themes and insights, while closed-ended and ranking responses were assessed using descriptive statistics (i.e., frequency and proportion counts). Drawing on prior applications of policy instrument typologies in circular economy research [33], the Delphi results were synthesised using a structured table linking identified challenges, success factors, political measures and instruments.

As outlined earlier, participation increased across rounds, reflecting the study's broadening scope and engagement. This flexible design, consistent with Delphi principles [56], allowed for interdisciplinary expansion without compromising methodological integrity.

Data collection took place between August and October 2024, allowing sufficient time between rounds for analysis, iteration and targeted participant recruitment. The full survey instruments for Rounds 1 and 2, along with the discussion prompts used in the final workshop, are provided in Supplementary Table S2.

4. Findings

This section presents the findings of the three-round Delphi study, designed to explore the enabling conditions for mainstreaming bio-methane production as part of Ireland's CBE. Grounded in Roth's [18, 19] market design framework, the study identifies the key tasks that such marketplaces and allocation systems must accomplish to function effectively.

4.1. Brainstorming (survey 1)

The initial round of the Delphi study used a survey to explore foundational challenges and opportunities for developing CBMs in Ireland's dairy sector. The survey recorded expert perspectives on broad, interacting conditions relating to CBMs, including policy, finance, infrastructure and nutrient circularity. Nineteen experts from academia, policy, finance and industry participated in Round 1, highlighting a range of systemic and interconnected drivers, barriers and risks.

In response to a question on how to incentivise an integrated approach for the dairy sector to exploit AD, biorefining and other bio-based opportunities, a qualitative content analysis of expert responses revealed several recurring themes. Government funding and financial incentives were most frequently cited, followed by infrastructure and technical integration, market development, policy clarity, collaboration and knowledge sharing (Supplementary Table S3).

Participants were asked to identify the main risks they associate with investing in circular economy and bioeconomy opportunities. Here, financial uncertainty—including concerns about revenue shortfalls, instability and unpredictability—was cited by 58 % of respondents as the most critical risk (Fig. 8[a], Appendix B). In response to a related question on barriers to implementation, misaligned regulatory frameworks emerged as the most significant policy-related concern, mentioned by 32 % of participants (Fig. 8[b], Appendix B). Experts also emphasised the importance of coordinated action and systemic

Fig. 4. The modified Delphi process (Adapted from Okoli and Pawlowski [49], de Jesus et al. [54] and Schmidt et al. [62]).

approaches, warning that fragmented efforts could fail to generate the necessary momentum. As one participant observed, “*If we want to do this, it will require all the levers of change to be pulled simultaneously.*”¹

On research and investment priorities, there was near-unanimous agreement (95 %) on the need for further funding to support infrastructure and demonstration sites (Fig. 8[c], Appendix B). Many participants also stressed that investment in technology R&D and pilot-scale trials is essential to bridge knowledge gaps and build confidence in the scalability of CBE solutions (Fig. 8[d], Appendix B).

4.2. Narrowing down (survey 2) and validation (concluding workshop)

The three-round Delphi process was designed to move from broad exploration to targeted action. In Survey 1, participants engaged in an open-ended brainstorming exercise to surface key barriers, opportunities and knowledge gaps related to CBE development in the dairy sector. These insights formed the foundation for Survey 2, where a larger panel of experts was asked to prioritise the most critical risks to CBM implementation, using Tuni et al.’s [20] ex-ante risk classification across five domains: supply, market, finance, policy/regulation and technology.

Fig. 5 presents the results for four of these domains—supply, market, finance and policy/regulation—highlighting the most frequently cited risks within each. These survey findings informed the structure of the Round 3 workshop, where participants worked collaboratively to validate the rankings and co-develop practical responses. The outcomes of these discussions are synthesised in Tables 2–5, which align with the core domains of supply, market, finance and policy/regulation. Each table outlines (i) the specific concern raised, (ii) the success factors identified by participants, (iii) proposed political measures and (iv) the types of instruments (regulatory, economic, informational, etc.) needed to support implementation.

Technical risks, while assessed in Survey 2, are presented separately in Fig. 6. These results offer insights into TRLs and implementation challenges across key components of the biorefinery system – such as anaerobic digestion, feedstock enhancement and nutrient circularity. While not expanded into a dedicated table, these findings contributed to broader discussions around innovation capacity and deployment readiness, particularly in relation to workforce constraints and low-TRL

technologies.

The following sections explore these domains in greater detail, outlining the specific barriers identified, the solutions proposed by participants, and the implications for building a robust and inclusive biomethane market grounded in CBE principles.

4.2.1. Supply risks

The primary supply risk identified in Survey 2 was “feedstock availability” (68 %) (Fig. 5[a]). Seasonal variability, inconsistent quality and insufficient supply chains were highlighted as critical concerns. Table 2 outlines the key challenges and strategies proposed to mitigate these issues, including feedstock diversification, localised supply strategies and cooperative initiatives.

4.2.2. Market risks

Building on the supply-side challenges, the primary market risks identified in Survey 2 were “market forecast demand risk” (39 %) and “consumer perception (quality vs. new products)” (29 %) (Fig. 5[b]). These concerns emphasise uncertainties around demand size and consumer trust in bio-based products. Table 3 highlights strategies for market activation, such as price-based incentives, independent product validation and public awareness campaigns.

4.2.3. Policy and regulatory risks

The primary policy and regulatory risks identified in survey 2 were “public policy and institutional” (35 %) and “regulatory standards” (23 %) (Fig. 5[c]). Table 4 highlights the concerns associated with these risks, such as inconsistent regulations and the misalignment of sectoral incentives. Strategies include harmonising EU and national standards, enforcing end-of-waste criteria and integrating nutrient management plans with land use policies. These measures aim to ensure that policy frameworks facilitate rather than hinder the development of CBMs.

4.2.4. Finance risks

The primary financial risk identified in Survey 2 was “capital costs” (62 %) (Fig. 5[d]). This risk highlights the substantial upfront investment required to establish AD plant and related technologies. Table 5 outlines key challenges associated with these financial barriers, including the risk of stranded assets and limited investor confidence.

4.2.5. Technical risks

Fig. 6 reveals that more mature technologies like AD and feedstock enhancement face greater human resource constraints, suggesting

¹ Hereafter, all direct quotes from participants are presented in italics and enclosed in quotation marks.

Fig. 5. Summary of the key risks identified during Round 2 of the Delphi process, categorised into (a) supply, (b) market, (c) policy/regulatory and (d) finance domains. (N = 31).

Table 2
Key challenges and proposed solutions for stabilising feedstock supply in the CBE.

Concern	Success factor(s)	Political measure(s)	Instrument (s)
Supply availability and quality (incl. seasonality)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Strategic oversight of supply chains. – Localised strategies based on feedstock quality and accessibility. – Investigate the use of scalable AD technology at the organisational level. – Diversify feedstock sources. – Input quality criteria considering nutrient management practices. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Geographical planning and regional supply chain development. – Facilitate alternative feedstock integration. 	All
Lack of monitoring for potential feedstocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Create a comprehensive feedstock database, including technical characteristics and untapped sources. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Public-funded database development 	Research and Education
Feedstock competition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Develop cooperative models to align interests and ensure long-term farmer engagement – de-risk business models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Policy frameworks to encourage cooperative supply agreements with fair competition policies. 	Economic

workforce capacity issues at deployment stage. In contrast, high technical risk scores for conversion technologies and carbon capture indicate low technology readiness levels (TRLs) and innovation-stage challenges. Quality concerns for nutrient circularity and broader biorefining reflect lingering uncertainty or limited trust in the performance of circular solutions.

4.3. Implications for market design – infrastructure, rules, customs and social support

Following Roth’s [19] market design framework expert insights were organised around four key pillars: infrastructure, rules, customs and social support.

Table 3
Key challenges and proposed solutions for addressing uncertainty around the market size and consumer perceptions surrounding the quality of these new bio-based products.

Concern	Success factor(s)	Political measure(s)	Instrument(s)
Access to grid infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Invest in grid infrastructure and develop regional configurations for better resource flow. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Allocate public funding and implement supportive policies for market accessibility. 	Economic
Market activation and price volatility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Incentivise renewable components in fertiliser and renewable energy, e. g., price-based incentives, long-term off-take agreements and feed-in tariffs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Extending from the Renewable Heat Obligation (RHO) to support pricing guarantees and market stability for all core products. 	Regulatory, Economic
Demand uncertainties for digestate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Recognise outputs as co-products and by-products instead of “waste” to enhance marketability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Standardised rules and guidelines for digestate use to support farmer engagement in how they may be used to displace chemical fertilisers. 	Regulatory
Consumer perception of bio-based products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Independent validation to build trust in quality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Eco-labelling and public awareness campaigns. 	Informational
Community buy-in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Integrate communities into the value chain to address resistance to AD plants. – Creating a level playing for small and large businesses to participate equally. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Social impacts assessments and equitable value-sharing mechanisms. 	Research and Education, Economic

4.3.1. Infrastructure: Building the foundations for circular biomethane markets

Participants emphasised the need to undertake pilot projects and demonstrations. These initiatives could serve as proof-of-concept models, building investor confidence and identifying potential bottlenecks. Funding for these commercial demonstrations was noted as

Table 4

Key challenges and proposed solutions to overcome policy and regulatory risks to CBM development.

Concern	Success factor	Political measure	Instrument(s)
Strategic policy and regulatory gaps	– Translate European regulation to a national level. – Develop cross-sectoral strategies and streamline regulations for clarity.	– Adopt a whole-of-government approach and harmonise national and EU regulations. – Enforce End-of-waste criteria.	Regulatory, Informational
Risk of linear industry development	– Ensure circular approaches, emphasising co-products like digestate.	– Include all renewable components in political frameworks.	Regulatory, Economic
Nutrient circularity and waterways protection	– Integrate land management plans into circular bioeconomy strategies.	– Update regulations for organic residues to enable resource valorisation.	Regulatory
Regulatory bottlenecks	– Expedite approvals with pre-validation process for new technologies and pre-approved facility locations.	– Pilot fast-track mechanisms for AD-related projects. – Flexibility for early adopters.	Regulatory
Industry-government disconnection	– Create policy forums and consultation mechanisms to shape CBE legislation collaboratively.	– Mechanisms for industry-government collaboration.	Informational, Regulatory
Limited public awareness	– Broad educational campaigns on regulatory objectives.	– Publicly funded informational initiatives.	Informational

essential, with financial instruments like the “*Just Transition Fund*” playing a critical role (BOR 2).² The absence of a comprehensive database on feedstock availability was identified by participants as a significant constraint for scaling AD projects. Participants highlighted the importance of cataloguing technical characteristics and exploring alternative feedstocks; “*many potential feedstocks are not monitored or not accessed typically in digester plants (BOR 1).*” Such a database would facilitate informed decision-making and help to diversify feedstock supply chains, reducing dependency on single sources.

There was an observed consensus that regional configurations and pre-approved AD plant locations would minimise congestion and reduce resource competition. Breakout groups acknowledged that, “*as the dairy sector moves from a linear to a circular economy, will that drive certain competitive behaviours as well? As everybody is scrambling for access to the biogas, to the feedstock, to the digestate (BOR 1).*” Addressing this concern, spatial analysis was deemed essential to optimise plant locations and prevent stranded assets. “*So how many of these do we need? Where do we need them? That kind of a spatial analysis is very important to avoid stranded assets, because these are 25-to-30-year investments (BOR 4)*” Integrating local authorities into planning processes, while addressing their limited technical expertise, was viewed as critical to streamlining implementation and ensuring the scalability of AD projects.

A consensus emerged on the need for standardised and modular AD technology to mitigate operational risks and ensure scalability. One participant stressed, “*We do not want ‘mom-and-pop’ scale setups here. We*

² Quotes attributed to breakout rooms (BORs) refer to summary statements delivered in the main session by nominated representatives—typically the moderator or domain expert—from each BOR. A breakdown of the breakout rooms and associated participant roles is provided in Figure 7, Appendix A.

Table 5

Key challenges and proposed solutions for alleviating concerns about capital costs when implementing CBE initiatives.

Concern	Success factor	Political measure	Instrument (s)
High upfront capital costs for AD plant and related technologies	– Reduce costs through economies of scale, modular technology and further R&D to de-risk the business model.	– Provide capital grants, tax incentives and low-interest loans to reduce initial financial burdens.	Economic, Research and Education
Lack of tailored financial products	– Access to tailored financial products such as sustainability-linked bonds and innovative loan designs.	– Facilitate partnerships with financial institutions such like the EIB and sovereign funds.	Economic
Uncertainty in long-term funding for CBE projects.	– Assurances on funding sources available over the longer term.	– Establish multi-annual government funding commitments to ensure continuity.	Economic
Risk of stranded assets due to technological or market shifts	– Conduct spatial analysis to optimise facility locations and prevent over-investment.	– Promote standardised engineering designs for scalability and operational flexibility as required. – Geographical planning.	Research and Education
Challenges in financing auxiliary infrastructure (e. g., storage facilities)	– Broaden funding access to include auxiliary infrastructure needed for bioeconomy systems.	– Support holistic funding models covering complete value chains, not just primary facilities.	Economic
Low margins in CE projects limiting private sector investment.	– Incentivise value-added product development to enhance profitability.	– Create product-specific purchase obligations (similar to the RHO for biomethane) and promote further market activation mechanisms to provide revenue assurances.	Economic

want larger scale and replicable models (BOR 4),” while highlighting the importance of partnering with major international technology providers to support early-stage operations. Further research and development is vital to support lower TRLs and lower business model risk. Participants suggested that government-backed funding for infrastructure projects should include obligations to explore innovative technologies.

By prioritising innovation, scalability and strategic planning, these measures aim to address key challenges and unlock the potential of CBMs in the dairy sector.

4.3.2. Rules: Establishing governance and standards

Establishing clear and enforceable rules is critical to ensuring the integrity and functionality of the biomethane market. A key issue raised by participants was the classification of digestate and other recovered outputs, where inconsistent regulatory definitions create uncertainty and hinder market adoption. Participants emphasised that reclassifying digestate as a “*co-product*” or “*by-product*” rather than “*waste*” would enhance its marketability and alleviate consumer concerns (BOR 5). Similarly, “*standardisation on how the solid waste could be reused is important to remove risk from the system as a whole (BOR 1).*” Local regulatory adaptation was also highlighted as necessary to align

Fig. 6. Summary of the key technical risks for each technology as identified during round 2 of the Delphi process. ($N = 31$).

biomethane outputs with sustainability goals. "We need to adopt RENURE standards for local regulations and conduct life cycle assessments to align outputs with sustainability goals (BOR 3)."

The alignment of national policies with EU regulations was another major concern. Ireland's stricter interpretation of waste regulations compared to other jurisdictions was seen as an obstacle to investment. "The interpretation of waste here is much stricter than in the UK or Europe. A mechanism to test regulations across jurisdictions could clarify discrepancies (BOR 4)." However, while this view reflects the concerns raised by actors on the ground, it may be influenced by planning and permitting challenges rather than regulatory text itself. As another observer noted, Ireland in fact relies heavily on EU derogations (e.g., under the Nitrates and Sewage Sludge Directives), which suggests that the stricter interpretation may be more of a practical or procedural perception than a legal one. This highlights a key distinction between perceived and actual regulatory restrictiveness—both of which can shape investor confidence and uptake. In addition, regulatory alignment with EU taxonomy and certification standards was seen as crucial to ensuring compliance and avoiding penalties. "We can't ignore the fines coming down the tracks here. Robust certification is going to be important, especially under CSRD reporting requirements (BOR 5)."

The need for clear contractual agreements for feedstock supply and digestate use was also highlighted. Uncertainty around long-term contracts was seen as a barrier to market participation, with participants calling for economic models that fairly distribute value across the supply chain. Additionally, the challenge of managing surplus nutrients and ensuring regulatory compliance was emphasised. "We need economic models to address surplus nutrients and ensure regulatory compliance (BOR 4)."

Establishing clear regulatory frameworks, certification systems and contractual agreements are essential to reducing investment uncertainty, increasing participation and aligning the biomethane market with broader CBE objectives.

4.3.3. Customs: Establishing collaborative practices and market norms

Participants emphasised the importance of cooperative ownership models to ensure long-term stability in the biomethane market. The direct involvement of farmers in AD plant ownership and operation was seen as a critical strategy for securing feedstock supply. "Farmers should be very much involved in the owning and running of these plants, and that would ensure they have a long-term interest in maintaining supply (BOR 1)." Cooperatives were also viewed as an effective risk-sharing mechanism, providing stability for both producers and processors. "A cooperative model is the best way to alleviate concerns about supply risks and help de-risk

these types of business models (BOR 3)."

Scaling biorefining operations was seen as dependent on cooperative leadership and public-private partnerships, balancing community benefits with centralised governance. "Biorefining at scale is going to be more efficient, but we need leadership, particularly from cooperatives, to support economies of scale (BOR 3)." Participants also saw potential in integrating partnerships between industry, government and local communities to maximise long-term economic sustainability.

The Renewable Heat Obligation (RHO) was recognised as an important driver of biomethane production, but participants questioned whether it adequately supports co-products like digestate. "The RHO is designed to create a market for biomethane and raise the price. But will that filter down to other core products as well (BOR 4)?" A whole-of-government approach was seen as essential to ensuring that policy mechanisms effectively incentivise all value-added products such as bio-based fertilisers. Participants recommended retailer obligations to incorporate renewable nitrogen or phosphorus in fertilisers, which could help activate local markets for digestate.

The need for adaptable business models that reflect local conditions was also widely acknowledged. Given variations in feedstock availability, market access and infrastructure, a one-size-fits-all approach was deemed ineffective. "There's no one-size-fits-all model in terms of business model—whether it's grid access, feedstocks or market price, there's a lot of moving parts and a lot of stakeholders to engage with (BOR 4)." Long-term policy incentives, such as tax reductions or operational subsidies, were also seen as more effective than one-off capital grants in ensuring sustained market participation.

Promoting cooperative ownership, targeted market activation and adaptable business models emerged as points of consensus and were viewed as crucial components for supporting a circular business model for biorefining and nutrient circularity.

4.3.4. Social support: Building trust and engagement across all stakeholders

Social support is essential for promoting collaboration and long-term commitment among stakeholders in the biomethane market. A key aspect of this is integrating local communities into the value chain, which is critical to overcoming resistance to biorefinery plant siting. Participants stress that treating communities as integral participants and not just peripherals, is crucial. Despite this acknowledgement, strong opposition has previously persisted. One participant observed that "any proposed siting of anaerobic digesters anywhere in the country has been met by very stern opposition, mainly related to feedstock transport and that has to be considered (BOR 2)." Transparent engagement processes and mechanisms to share benefits with local stakeholders were identified as

essential for addressing these concerns.

A cultural shift toward accepting CE products requires targeted education initiatives and independent validation mechanisms to build consumer trust. One participant remarked, “*who do consumers believe when claims are made about products (BOR 3)?*” Independent validation is critical to help with consumer support. Education was also viewed as essential for all stakeholders, with one participant noting, “*an educational piece for all actors in this space is necessary—this really falls on the government to get everyone up to speed (BOR 1).*” Across the board, participants emphasised the urgent need for better information, communication and engagement to advance the integration of CBE practices.

Collaboration between industry and government is critical to aligning interests and ensuring future market developments. Participants stressed the importance of balancing government leadership with industry-driven innovation. As one participant observed, “*The government can set the framework, but industry needs to deliver on that framework (BOR 3).*” A science-based approach to policymaking, with mechanisms for industry input, was identified as crucial. Collaboration also requires reconciling sectoral benefits, particularly between the energy sector, which accrues decarbonisation benefits, and the agricultural sector, which supplies feedstock. Similarly, it was agreed that there is a need to align the pace of regulatory and policy change with industry solutions, ensuring they are compatible and synchronised.

Social support mechanisms can ensure equitable participation and sustained market success by addressing community concerns, driving cultural shifts and facilitating collaboration between industry, government and regulators.

5. Discussion: Pathways for systemic change

The current study identified a range of systemic risks and enabling conditions that shape the future development of biomethane markets within Ireland’s dairy sector. While the immediate focus is on biomethane, the underlying objective is to support the emergence of CBMs that generate renewable energy, advance nutrient circularity and align with broader environmental and agricultural goals. These insights were gathered through a modified Delphi process, in which financial uncertainty, high capital costs, regulatory ambiguity, supply chain challenges and underdeveloped markets for co-products such as digestate were identified as significant barriers to CBE adoption. The study applied Tuni et al.’s [20] ex-ante framework to structure the identification and interpretation of these risks across five key domains: supply, market, finance, policy/regulatory and technical. This proved essential in identifying key sources of uncertainty and where targeted interventions could facilitate investment and adoption.

In order to further interpret these insights, the study drew on Roth’s [19] market design framework, which identifies infrastructure, rules, customs and social support as the foundational elements of well-functioning markets that enable effective information exchange and transaction efficiency. This framing simplifies the complexity of biomethane development by conceptualising it as a transactional system, spanning from the supply of nutrients into digesters to the demand for outputs such as renewable energy and digestate. Collectively, these frameworks provide an integrated approach to identifying where the current system falls short and the conditions required for a biomethane market to emerge and function effectively.

The discussion now turns to RQ2, which considers the enabling conditions for a CBE capable of addressing excess nutrients from industrial agriculture. Whereas RQ1 focused on barriers to biomethane market development, RQ2 shifts attention to the broader structural and institutional conditions required to sustain circular outcomes across economic, environmental and social dimensions.

Insights from the Delphi process highlight that participants did not view biomethane development solely through a bioenergy lens, but as embedded within wider system challenges, including nutrient management, environmental protection and agricultural sustainability. This reflects the realities of the dairy sector, where waste management and resource use are intrinsically linked to production systems. As such, the transition towards CBMs depends on the alignment of market viability, environmental performance and social legitimacy, rather than progress along any single dimension in isolation. This interpretation is consistent with broader literature on the circular economy–decarbonisation–bioeconomy nexus, which emphasises the interdependencies between these domains and the need for integrated policy and governance approaches [63,64].

In the Irish context, this systemic misalignment is particularly evident. Despite exhibiting many of the structural conditions typically associated with successful biomethane deployment, including a large livestock base, concentrated agricultural production and increasing policy support, the sector remains underdeveloped compared to other European contexts. While economic barriers, particularly financial uncertainty and capital costs, represent the most immediate constraints identified in this study, the persistence of underdevelopment suggests that limitations extend beyond technical feasibility and market conditions alone, pointing to the importance of institutional coordination, governance and broader system integration.

5.1. Social legitimacy and acceptance in biomethane development

While the literature increasingly highlights biomethane’s potential to support sustainable production and consumption, the social dimensions of its deployment remain comparatively under-examined [63]. The findings of this study suggest that uncertainty around governance, responsibility allocation and co-product management can undermine understanding, confidence and participation across the value chain, thereby shaping perceptions of biomethane’s role in sustainable development. Emerging evidence suggests that increased knowledge of biomethane development is positively associated with stronger recognition of its role in sustainable development. However, this relationship is not straightforward and is mediated by trust, governance clarity and perceived fairness [63,65].

These patterns are reflected throughout our findings, which highlight that knowledge deficits and information asymmetries can reinforce uncertainty and scepticism, while targeted engagement processes can improve public perception and acceptance. From a market design perspective, these challenges relate directly to Roth’s [19,20] emphasis on social support, customs and the mitigation of repugnance. Where rules are unclear, responsibilities contested or benefits unevenly distributed, markets struggle to gain legitimacy regardless of technical feasibility.

This also clarifies the role of repugnance and NIMBY dynamics introduced earlier. Rather than representing irrational resistance to renewable energy, such responses often reflect concerns related to local impacts, lack of trust in governance and perceived inequities in how costs and benefits are distributed [65,66]. In this sense, opposition becomes a diagnostic signal of misalignment between project design, institutional arrangements and community expectations. Existing empirical evidence further shows that such resistance is amplified where large-scale facilities, perceived environmental externalities and limited opportunities for local participation intersect, reinforcing the importance of place-based approaches and early-stage engagement [40,67]. Accordingly, participatory governance, transparent communication and equitable benefit-sharing emerge as essential institutional mechanisms through which legitimacy is constructed and maintained, as consistently

observed across biomethane and biogas developments in different territorial contexts [63,65–67]. Social acceptance therefore emerges not as a downstream communication issue, but as a constitutive condition of biomethane market formation.

These dynamics are increasingly visible in planning and permitting contexts in Ireland, where proposed biogas and biomethane developments have encountered resistance linked to siting, environmental concerns and limited consultation, despite their alignment with national decarbonisation strategies [68]. Rather than treating social acceptance as a peripheral concern, these experiences highlight that legitimacy across both market participants and affected communities is a central enabling condition for biomethane development.

In contexts such as Ireland, where feedstock availability, policy ambition and scale potential are comparatively favourable, the persistence of resistance and delay underscores the importance of governance arrangements that actively embed social legitimacy alongside technical, environmental and economic considerations.

5.2. System design, circularity and governance challenges

Beyond social legitimacy, the findings highlight a second critical condition: the need to ensure that biomethane development delivers genuine circular outcomes within a coherent and integrated governance framework. This is particularly relevant in the Irish context, where intensive livestock production places significant pressure on nutrient management systems and freshwater ecosystems, while simultaneously generating nutrient resources that are central to agricultural productivity [69]. Manure and organic residues are not simply waste streams, but key inputs within farm nutrient cycles, underpinning soil fertility and reducing reliance on chemical fertilisers.

Against this backdrop, a key insight from this study is that Ireland's biomethane strategy risks failure if critical elements of circularity are not addressed. While the biorefinery process is generally well understood and supported, participants noted that attention remains focused on energy outputs, with insufficient emphasis on nutrient circularity. In particular, digestate – the nutrient-rich by-product of biorefining – remains underexplored despite its potential to displace chemical fertilisers and contribute to soil health.

Although the National Biomethane Strategy refers to digestate as a nutrient-rich bio-based fertiliser, this treatment oversimplifies the issue. Lamolinara et al. [70] warn that digestate can contribute to nutrient pollution if not managed carefully, while Feng et al. [71] emphasise that its safe reintegration is essential to closing nutrient loops. While the strategy assigns responsibility for further research, the absence of clear regulatory pathways and incentives raises concerns. Digestate is not merely a by-product but a central component of circularity, reinforcing that the environmental benefits of biomethane production are highly context-dependent and contingent on effective co-product management rather than inherent solely to the technology itself [72,73].

Participants emphasised the need for standardised rules and technical guidance aligned with water quality and nitrate regulations. As highlighted in the Environmental Protection Agency's (EPA) submission to the Draft National Biomethane Strategy [74], digestate management must not undermine water quality objectives, particularly in nutrient-sensitive regions where land application capacity is already constrained. Without robust soil testing, nutrient management planning and regional coordination, increased digestate volumes could exacerbate nutrient runoff [74]. From a market design perspective, this gap challenges Roth's [19] principle of safety, as transactions perceived as environmentally or regulatorily risky are less likely to attract participation.

Achieving circularity depends on the alignment of policy frameworks across sectors. Participants highlighted a fragmented and siloed

approach, in which biomethane policy remains insufficiently integrated with land, water and fertiliser governance. While the national strategy links biomethane to decarbonisation, it continues to prioritise energy outputs without fully embedding circularity within system design. As noted by the OECD [75, p.72], Ireland's regulatory framework is “*at best, not conducive to circular business and, at worst, incentivises linear business models.*” Such conditions undermine integrated system development and reinforce energy-centric, rather than circular, outcomes.

This fragmentation is reflected in the distribution of responsibilities and benefits across sectors. Participants questioned where responsibility for GHG emission reductions lies, given that agriculture supplies the feedstock while the energy sector captures emissions accounting benefits. The strategy reflects this ambiguity, with emissions savings formally attributed to energy, while agricultural actors derive only indirect benefits [14]. Failure to integrate co-products such as digestate weakens the overall value proposition, while ambiguity over decarbonisation benefits complicate efforts to align incentives across sectors [76].

As a renewable gas compatible with existing infrastructure, biomethane has the potential to substitute fossil-derived natural gas and contribute to energy security, particularly in the context of geopolitical instability and volatile gas markets [14,77–80]. Recent estimates suggest that biomethane could offset up to 29 % of global natural gas use, significantly reduce reliance on imports and, in some European contexts – including Ireland – has the technical potential to fully replace natural gas imports from Russia, while also reducing emissions from gas systems by approximately 11 % [77]. In this respect, its capacity to displace fossil-derived gas is a critical component in maintaining a trajectory toward energy system decarbonisation. Thus, biomethane can be understood as an integrated model of the CBE, combining renewable energy production, waste valorisation and nutrient recycling within a single system. This aligns closely with broader sustainable development objectives, including the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly those related to climate action, responsible consumption and production, and affordable and clean energy.

Similarly, its integration within agricultural practices offers a pathway to address GHG emissions from a difficult-to-abate sector through the conversion of residues into renewable energy and nutrient recovery. However, these outcomes are not automatic. While biomethane has the potential to function as a “virtuous” model of a CBE – aligned with broader sustainable development objectives and capable of substituting fossil-derived natural gas – this potential depends on how effectively these systems are designed, governed and embedded within their wider social and environmental context. Without this, there is a risk that biomethane development remains narrowly focused on energy production, limiting its broader environmental and systemic benefits. In this sense, a narrow focus on energy and climate objectives risks displacing rather than resolving underlying system challenges, with unintended consequences emerging across nutrient management, environmental protection and social acceptance.

Underlying these challenges is a deeper political economy issue. Participants highlighted persistent difficulties in achieving long-term coordination and systems thinking within Irish policy, resulting in fragmented regulatory landscapes and delayed infrastructure development [81]. While the national strategy identifies sustainability as one of five pillars [14], the findings suggest it should operate as an overarching principle guiding all dimensions of implementation. As Devaney and Henchion [82] and the OECD [83] argue, circular transitions require a shift in policy and institutional thinking capable of overcoming vested interests and enabling systemic change.

Ultimately, the study highlights the need for a more integrated approach that supports energy objectives while simultaneously enabling viable markets for the co-products of biorefining. Policymakers must foster transparent and coherent regulatory environments, while

agribusinesses explore models aligned with CBE principles. Positioning biorefining within interconnected climate, energy and circular transitions – while incorporating biodiversity and social considerations – ensures that biomethane is not treated solely as a bioenergy solution, but as a cornerstone of a broader sustainable development pathway [84].

5.3. Incentive mechanisms and risk sharing

While the preceding sub-sections highlighted the importance of social legitimacy and system integration, this section focuses on incentive structures and risk-sharing mechanisms among actors directly involved in the biomethane and biorefining value chain.

The role of financial uncertainty as a key barrier to investment was a consistent theme across expert contributions. Participants emphasised that long payback periods, high upfront costs and uncertainty around future revenue streams severely limit project bankability. These concerns mirror the work of Gloy and Dressler [85], who argue that the capital-intensive nature of biorefining often deters private investment, particularly when environmental benefits are not priced into market transactions. Despite growing political attention and recent public funding commitments (€40 million government funding allocation for biomethane expansion and the RHO) [14], current support remains too narrow and primarily focused on capital costs and energy production. Participants stressed the need for broader financial mechanisms, including operational support, feedstock storage and digestate valorisation. Without these, risk remains concentrated among project developers and supply chain actors, particularly farmers, who are least equipped to absorb it.

Ensuring that farmers are not left carrying disproportionate risk was a recurring concern. Participants cautioned against a model in which farmers are treated solely as feedstock providers, disconnected from value creation or decision-making. This reflects broader concerns regarding power imbalances in bioeconomy systems, where primary producers often capture limited value despite bearing significant operational risks [86]. For the transition to be equitable and sustainable, farmers must have opportunities to participate in ownership structures and governance arrangements. Cooperative-led models were highlighted as a viable solution. Ireland's strong tradition of cooperative organisation provides a foundation for collective investment, risk-sharing and improved access to finance [87]. While cooperatives can address market failures by pooling resources and strengthening bargaining power [88,89], evidence from the biogas sector suggests that practical challenges such as trust, coordination and perceived fairness must be addressed to ensure their effectiveness [90].

Participants also pointed to the potential of flexible financial instruments, such as those used in the *MilkFlex* loan scheme, to help derisk investment. The *MilkFlex* loan scheme was introduced following the abolition of milk quotas in 2015 to support the expansion of Ireland's dairy sector through flexible, unsecured financing [91]. The success of *MilkFlex* in mitigating risk and enabling farmers to invest in growth demonstrates how similar financial models could be adapted for biorefining, ensuring that financing options remain accessible while being responsive to market risks. Adapting similar tools to biorefining, linked to feedstock flows or energy prices, could expand access to capital and improve project viability for small and medium-scale actors.

In sum, unlocking biomethane investment requires an integrated strategy that includes public incentives, risk-sharing financial models and institutional structures to promote inclusive participation. Rather than relying solely on large-scale developers or top-down grants, a diversified financing ecosystem is needed to recognise the distinct roles of farmers, cooperatives, lenders and the state. Participants argued that policies must reflect the entire value chain, not just the energy output, including investment in knowledge transfer, advisory services and

training to build capacity at the local level. By coupling financial innovation with inclusive governance, Ireland can scale biorefining in an economically viable and socially resilient way.

Without these supports, the sector risks being dominated by a small number of actors, with limited uptake and uneven distribution of benefits. Ensuring that CBE transitions deliver fair outcomes will require rethinking not just who participates in the market, but also how risks and rewards are shared across the entire value chain.

6. Conclusion, limitations and future research directions

This study was motivated by two interconnected developments: increasing environmental pressures from excess nutrient pollution in Irish agriculture and the policy momentum created by Ireland's biomethane strategy. Using a modified Delphi approach, it identified the enabling conditions for a CBE that addresses these challenges, rather than focusing solely on expanding biogas production. By engaging upstream stakeholders, the study highlighted key financial, regulatory and operational risks, emphasising the need to move beyond energy-centric approaches. Applying Tuni et al.'s [20] ex-ante risk framework and Roth's [18,19] market design lens provided a structured diagnosis of the barriers to effective biomethane and biorefinery development.

A central finding is that while biorefinery is technically viable and supported at policy level, current strategies lack clarity on how nutrient loop closure will be achieved. The primary opportunity – and challenge – lies in embedding circularity through co-product valorisation, particularly digestate. More broadly, biomethane's contribution to sustainable production and consumption depends on interrelated social, institutional and system-level conditions. Increased knowledge can strengthen recognition of its role in sustainable development, but this is mediated by trust, governance clarity and perceived fairness. Social acceptance is therefore actively constructed through transparent communication, participatory governance and equitable benefit-sharing. At the same time, biomethane must be embedded within a CBE framework that simultaneously supports the displacement of fossil-derived natural gas, nutrient recovery and environmental protection. Realising this potential depends on overcoming coordination failures across policy domains and ensuring a more equitable distribution of risks and rewards across the value chain.

These findings align with broader concerns in the literature that poorly integrated CBE transitions may reproduce existing environmental and economic inequalities [92]. A "just transition" perspective is therefore essential, ensuring that policy frameworks reflect the interconnected nature of energy, land use and sustainability goals. Biomethane can support climate mitigation, responsible production and energy decarbonisation, but only where circularity, social legitimacy and environmental safeguards are actively embedded within system design.

The study focused on upstream actors – including processors, finance experts and policymakers – given their role in shaping market structures. While deliberate, this limits inclusiveness, particularly regarding farmers and impacted communities. In addition, the national focus reflects the specific characteristics of Irish agriculture, including its grass-based systems and spatial concentration, which limit direct international comparison. These constraints highlight the need for caution in generalising findings, while also pointing to opportunities for future comparative and regional research.

Further research should examine the governance and technical dimensions of digestate use in greater depth. As digestate valorisation is central to the circular bioeconomy yet remains underregulated and poorly integrated into existing market systems, there is a pressing need to develop clear guidelines and monitoring frameworks. Future studies could investigate how digestate can be standardised, certified and safely

applied in a way that aligns with EU waste and fertiliser regulations. In parallel, further work is needed to pilot cooperative-led business models in real-world contexts, particularly in regions with differing feedstock availability and market maturity. Finally, applied research on financial instruments, such as adaptive loan structures or public-private co-financing schemes, could strengthen the evidence base for scaling inclusive and resilient biorefining systems.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve sentence structures and readability. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take (s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study consist of anonymised expert survey responses collected as part of a Delphi process. Due to confidentiality agreements with participants, the data are not publicly available. Anonymised data may be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supplementary materials

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Appendix

A. Participant Details

Fig. 7. Participant composition by role across breakout rooms.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ciarán Corrigan: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Fergal G. O’Brien:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Anne Marie Henihan:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Abigail Pattenden:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **JJ Leahy:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Vincent O’Flaherty:** Writing – review & editing. **John Garvey:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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B. Additional Tables and Findings

a. CE and CBE investment risk factor

b. Barriers to CE and CBE

c. Infrastructure and demonstration needs

d. CE and CBE research funding priorities

Fig. 8. Round 1 summary: expert views on risks (a), Barriers (b), Infrastructure (c) and Research needs(d). Note: questions (a)–(c) were single-response (closed-ended); question (d) allowed multiple responses.

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